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**VIRTUAL REALITY
HISTORY, APPLICATIONS AND FUTURE**

Lathika K.

Sr. Lecturer, Dept. of computer Science Srinivas Institute of Management Studies
Mangalore

ABSTRACT

Virtual reality is contending to be the interface of the future, allowing ordinary users to use their senses to interact with complex data. Virtual Reality (VR) and Virtual Environments (VE) are used in computer community interchangeably. VR is an interactive and immersive (with the feeling of presence) experience in a simulated (autonomous) world and this measure we will use to determine the level of advance of VR systems. Virtual Reality is an enabling technology that has wide applications in training, product design, etc. Virtual reality (VR) technology is being used to resolve problems in real-world situations. Virtual Reality Facilities (VRFs) simulate the action perception relationship in a physically correct manner but without involving real objects or real events. The National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) is using VR to train astronauts to repair the Hubble Space Telescope.

Keywords: Virtual Reality, Virtual Environment, Simulate, NASA, Hubble Space Telescope.

1. Introduction

1.1 History

Virtual reality (VR) means experiencing things through our computers that don't really exist. Virtual reality blocks the one off from the real world and substitutes a computer-generated alternative. It involves wearing a headset called a head-mounted display, putting on stereo headphones over your ears, and touching or feeling the surroundings using data gloves i.e gloves with built-in sensors. Using virtual reality one can run an Olympic 100 metres, sing onstage with rolling stones or go to Mars and many more things without leaving the house.

1.2 Early attempts at virtual reality

1.2.1 Panoramic paintings

The earliest attempt at virtual reality is surely from the nineteenth century. These paintings were intended to fill the viewer's entire field of vision, making them feel present at some historical event or scene.

1.2.2 1838 – Stereoscopic photos & viewers

In 1838 Charles Wheatstone's research demonstrated that the different two-dimensional images from each eye into a single object of three dimensions can be processed by the human brain. The popular Google Cardboard and low budget VR head mounted displays for mobile phones are used by the design principles of the Stereoscope.

1.2.3 1929 – Link Trainer, the First Flight Simulator

The "Link trainer" probably the first example of a commercial flight simulator was created by Edward Link in 1929, which was entirely electromechanical. It was controlled by motors that linked to the rudder and steering column to modify the pitch and roll.

1.2.4 1930s – Science fiction story predicted VR

In the 1930s a story by science fiction writer Stanley G. Weinbaum (Pygmalion's Spectacles) had the idea of a pair of eye glasses that let the wearer experience a imaginary world through holographics, smell, taste and touch.

1.2.5 1950s – Morton Heilig's Sensorama

An arcade-style theatre cabinet was developed by that cinematographer Morton Heilig in the mid 1950's that would stimulate all the senses, not just sight and sound. It contained stereo speakers, a stereoscopic 3D display, fans, smell generators and a vibrating chair. The intention of Sensorama was to fully involve the individual in the film.

1.2.6 1960 – The first VR Head Mounted Display

The next invention of Morton Heilig was the Telesphere Mask and this was the first example of a head-mounted display (HMD). The headset provided stereoscopic 3D and wide vision with stereo sound.

1.2.7 1961 Headsight – First motion tracking HMD

Two Philco Corporation engineers Comeau & Bryan in 1961 developed the first precursor to the Head Mounted Display – the **Headsight** as we know it today. It contained a video screen for each eye and a magnetic motion tracking system, which was linked to a closed circuit camera. Actually, the **Headsight** was not developed for virtual reality applications, but to allow for remote viewing of dangerous situations by the military.

1.2.8 1965 – The Ultimate display by Ivan Sutherland

Ivan Sutherland described the "Ultimate Display" concept. His concept included:

- A virtual world viewed through a HMD and appeared realistic through augmented 3D sound and tactile feedback.
- Computer hardware to create the virtual world and maintain it in real time.
- The ability users to interact with objects in the virtual world in a realistic way

1.2.9 1968 – Sword of Damocles

In 1968 Ivan Sutherland and his student **Bob Sproull** created the first VR / AR head mounted display (Sword of Damocles) that was connected to a computer. It was a large and scary looking device that was too heavy to be worn by any user comfortably. The user would also need to be tied into the device.

1.2.10 1969 – Artificial Reality

A series of experiences was developed by a computer artist **Myron Kruegere** in 1969, which he termed “artificial reality” in which he developed computer -generated environments that responded to the people in it. The projects named GLOWFLOW, METAPLAY, and PSYCHIC SPACE advancement in his research which ultimately cause the development of VIDEOPLACE technology. This technology allowed people to communicate with each other in a computer generated environment regardless of being miles apart.

1.2.11 1987 – Virtual reality the name was born

In 1987 **Jaron Lanier**, founder of the visual programming lab (VPL), invented the term “virtual reality”. A wide range of virtual reality equipments including the Data glove and the EyePhone head mounted display are developed through his company. They were the first company to sell Virtual Reality goggles.

1.2.12 1991 – Virtuality Group Arcade Machines

A range of arcade games and machines were launched by the Virtuality Group. Players would wear a set of VR goggles and play on gaming machines with real-time immersive stereoscopic 3D visuals.

1.2.13 1992 – The Lawnmower Man

In 1992, a movie called **The Lawnmower Man** movie got released and introduced the concept of virtual reality to a large audience. It was based on the founder of Virtual Reality Jaron Lanier and his early laboratory days. **Pierce Brosnan** played the role of Jaron, a scientist who used virtual reality therapy on a mentally disabled patient. Real virtual reality equipment from VPL research labs was used in the film and the director Brett Leonard, accepted to drawing inspiration from companies like VPL.

1.2.14 1993 – SEGA announce new VR glasses

In 1993 at the Consumer Electronics Show, SEGA announced the Sega VR headset for the Sega Genesis console. The wrap-around prototype glasses had head tracking, stereo sound and LCD screens in the visor. But this was a huge flop.

1.2.15 1995 – Nintendo Virtual Boy

The Nintendo Virtual Boy, originally known as VR-32 was a 3D gaming console that was considered to be the first ever portable console that could display true 3D graphics. It was first released in Japan and North America at a price of \$180 but it was a commercial failure in spite of price drops. The reasons for this failure were a lack of colour in graphics (games were in red and black), there was a lack of software support and it was difficult to use the console in a comfortable position. And they discontinued its production and sale in the following year.

1.2.16 1999 – The Matrix

The film *The Matrix* hits theatres in 1999. In the films the characters are living in a fully simulated world, with many completely unaware that they do not live in the real world. Although some previous films had played in illustrating virtual reality, such as *Tron* in 1982 and *Lawnmower Man* in 1992, *The Matrix* has a major cultural impact and brought the topic of simulated reality into the mainstream.

2. What is VR? What is VR not?

The **definition of virtual reality** comes from the definitions for both ‘virtual’ and ‘reality’. The definition of ‘virtual’ is near and reality is what we experience as human beings. So the term ‘virtual reality’ basically means ‘near-reality’.

2.1 In technical terms...

Technically Virtual reality is the term used to describe **a three-dimensional, computer generated environment** which can be examined and interacted with by a person. That person becomes part of this virtual world or is deeply involved with this environment and at the same time, is able to manipulate objects or perform a series of actions.

2.2 What’s the difference Between Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality?

Virtual Reality and Augmented reality are two sides of the same coin. In Augmented Reality artificial objects are assumed in the real environment; Virtual Reality creates an artificial environment to occupy.

The computer uses sensors and algorithms to determine the position and orientation of a camera in Augmented reality. AR technology then contributes the 3D graphics as they would appear from the viewpoint of the camera, superimposing the computer-generated images over a user’s view of the real world.

In **Virtual Reality**, the computer uses similar sensors and math. However, rather than locating a real camera within a physical environment, the position of the user's eyes are located within the simulated environment. If the user's head turns, the graphics react accordingly. Rather than compositing virtual objects and a real scene, VR technology creates a convincing, interactive world for the user.

Moreover, there are two important terms that must be mentioned when talking about VR: **Telepresence** and **Cyberspace**. They are both tightly coupled with VR, but have a slightly different context:

- **Telepresence:** The term used to describe a set of technologies, such as high definition audio, video, and other interactive elements that enable people to feel or appear as if they were present in a location which they are not physically in. Used mainly as a collaboration tool, telepresence is used by vendors, including Cisco to help create a more "in person" meeting experience over a converged network.
- **Cyberspace:** The space in which computer transactions occur, particularly transactions between different computers. We say that images and text on the Internet exist in cyberspace, for example. The term is also often used in conjunction with Virtual Reality, designating the imaginary place where virtual objects exist. For example, if a computer produces a picture of a building that allows the architect to "walk" through and see what a design would look like, the building is said to exist in cyberspace.

2.3 Applications of Virtual Reality

People are familiar with the term 'Virtual reality' but are uncertain about the uses of this technology. Here is a list of the many applications of virtual reality:

2.3.1 Virtual Reality in the Military

Military adopts Virtual reality for all three services army, navy and air force where it is used for training purposes. This is useful for training soldiers for fighting or other dangerous situations where they have to learn how to react to a particular situation.

In a virtual reality simulation there is no risk of death or a serious injury. They can re do a particular act, where they can be involved with the enemy in an environment without the real world risks. This has proven to be safer and less costly than traditional training methods.

2.3.2 Virtual Reality and Education

In Education, virtual reality is being increasingly used for teaching and learning situations. This allows a large group of students to interact with each other. For example, Solar Systems can be learnt by **astronomy students** and they can also understand how it works by physical engagement with the objects within. Planets can be moved, stars can be seen and a comet can also be tracked. This can help them to see how abstract concepts work in a three dimensional environment which makes them easier to understand and retain.

2.3.3 Virtual Reality in Healthcare

Healthcare is one of the biggest adopters of virtual reality which contains surgery simulation, phobia treatment, robotic surgery and skills training. The advantage of this technology is healthcare professionals can learn new skills as well as refresh existing ones and it doesn't cause any danger to the patients.

Virtual reality is often used as a diagnostic tool in that it allows doctors to arrive at a diagnosis in conjunction with other methods such as MRI scans. The need for unnecessary procedures or surgery is removed.

Robotic surgery is the most popular of this technology. Here surgery is performed by means of robotic device controlled by a human surgeon, which reduces time and risk of complications. Virtual reality has been also been used for training purposes. In the field of remote **telesurgery** also virtual reality is used in which surgery is performed by the surgeon at a separate location to the patient.

2.3.4 Virtual Reality in Entertainment

The entertainment industry is one of the most excited promotion of virtual reality, mostly in games and virtual worlds. But other equally popular areas include

- Galleries
- Theatre, e.g. interactive performances
- Virtual theme parks
- Discovery centres

2.3.5 Virtual Reality in Fashion

Virtual reality is used by the fashion industry in a variety of ways. These include:

- VR software for building virtual fashion stores
- 3D avatars (virtual humans) to help with clothes design
- Fashion show in Second Life
- 3D fashion portfolio

2.3.6 Virtual Reality in Business

In a number of ways virtual reality is used by the business community which include:

- Virtual tours of a business environment
- Training of new employees
- A 360 view of a product

In many businesses, virtual reality is a cost effective way of developing a product or service. For example it enables them to test a model without having to develop several versions of this which can be time consuming and expensive and it also allows detecting any design problems at an early stage which can then be dealt sooner.

2.3.7 Virtual Reality in Engineering

3D modelling tools and visualisation techniques are used in virtual reality engineering as part of the design process. This technology enables engineers to view their project in 3D and get a greater understanding of how it works. They can also spot any flaws or potential risks before implementation. Project can be observed within a safe environment and changes can be made as and where necessary. This saves both time and money.

2.3.8 Virtual Reality and Scientific Visualisation

Virtual reality is adopted in the field of scientific visualisation. Computer graphics are used to express complex ideas and scientific concepts in this field. For example molecular models or statistical results.

Abstract concepts can be communicated to to audience by means of scientific visualization. The audience can interact with these images, for example, viewing a molecular structure at different angles or as a means of problem solving.

2.3.9 Virtual Reality in Telecommunications

Telecommunications is another field which has utilised virtual reality technology, most importantly mobile communications which enables easy access to a variety of VR based projects. The main challenge to be dealt with is a medium which mainly relies upon tone of voice, intonation, gesture and body language as compared to spoken words.

Telecommunications can be used to help virtual reality systems such as surgery simulation or telemedicine. An example of this is remote surgery in which images from that surgery can be transmitted to various locations around the world. It also enables surgery to be performed in remote locations using robotic technology and virtual reality.

2.3.10 Virtual Reality in Film

Virtual Reality is a very common theme in science fiction movies, where it is often used a way to turn the fantastical into something that seems totally real. Some of the most popular movies which used virtual reality are

- TRON & TRON Legacy
- The Matrix series
- Vanilla Sky

3. The future of VR

The future of every new technology, including virtual reality, must be considered in two different aspects: technological and social. Technological aspects include new research directions and potential use of them for scientific aims. Social aspects include the influence of new inventions on people: individuals and society as a whole.

3.1 Research directions in VR

The idea of the ultimate virtual environment as stated by Sutherland means that VR should be indistinguishable from “real” reality (RR). Most of today’s VR applications do not conform to reality and have poor quality, but are still very useful and persuasive. Without doubt VR has a big potential, but must be improved a lot to allow more comfortable and intuitive interaction with virtual world.

There is need for mechanisms allowing people to easily adapt themselves and their behaviour from VR to reality and vice versa. To address these requirements better than current systems do, a lot of research must be carried out and new technologies must be developed.

3.1.1. Ergonomics of visual displays

Up to now, the major interest was paid to visual feedback and visual display technologies. Nevertheless the quality of nowadays shipped HMDs is far from ideal: resolution is significantly below eye's resolving capability, luminance and color ranges do not cover the whole eye's perception range i.e brightness range and gamut respectively and finally the field of view is relatively narrow. All these disadvantages make virtual worlds appear "artificial" and unreal, which severely contributes to the simulator sickness

An alternative approach for presenting images to VR user(s) are large projection screens. Images can be seen with bare eyes, have better brightness and resolution than typical HMDs. Stereo viewing is possible with light and comfortable LCD shutter- or polarization-glasses. For the full immersion CAVE type displays or recently introduced domed projection screens can be used. Toshiba Corporation has lately developed a "volume-scanning" display consisting of many slices of semi-transparent LCD screens. This new technology allows three-dimensional viewing of stereoscopic images without any additional equipment.

3.1.2. Tracking technologies

Today's tracking technologies have many limitations. First and foremost: in many cases the tracked volume is very restricted. In practice the user is bound very closely to some point in space (i.e. tracker reference point) and cannot walk around freely. Moreover, the quality of tracking is often not sufficient –most of currently used technologies are very sensitive to environmental conditions and introduce considerable latency.

An ideal tracker should be small and lightweight so that it can be comfortably worn by the user. The working volume for the inside tracking should be big enough to allow free walking. And at least, the tracker should be immune to any kind of interferences that would guarantee the equally high measurement precision in the whole volume

The idea of outside tracking is very promising. It may open new possible applications of VR, like navigation systems or place-sensitive information services. The currently existing Global Positioning System (GPS) does not offer quality of position measurement that is sufficient for virtual reality yet, but further development in this area may bring the required improvements. Such a high precision GPS in combination with source independent orientation. Tracking devices may become then a solution for medium quality but cheap and wide-spread global VR or AR systems.

3.1.3 Computing power and rendering architectures

Though the most powerful computers are used in VR, there is a continuing hunger for more MIPS and megabytes. More detailed and impressive scenes require more storage capacity, more CPU performance and graphical power. Therefore new processors and graphics boards are being developed in order to fulfil these needs.

To overcome limitations of standard rendering architectures some novel VR systems correct already rendered image before displaying it. Just to mention approaches that can be implemented on conventional workstations like image deflection, Z-buffer warping, image generation from the panoramic photograph or dynamically generated impostors. Other more complicated methods require custom hardware architectures like address recalculation pipeline, frameless rendering or “just in time pixels”.

3.1.4. User interfaces

Future interaction with virtual worlds should involve better input and output devices. Every input device should be at the same time an output device that supports appropriate haptic feedback. This is essential, because every action performed in the real world on some object causes a reaction of this object. Other senses must be included into the interaction process like audio output and voice recognition for verbal communication with computer and finally: taste and smell. Combination of all these sensations would widen information passing channels between computer and human and make virtual reality really realistic.

3.1.6. Biomedical research

Sophisticated input and output devices are some of the most expensive parts of VR systems. Current standard output and input devices are far below the satisfying quality. The improvement of them in terms of resolution, precision etc is extremely expensive.

To overcome these problems, biomedical signal processing could be used both for input and output. Muscle activity could be detected based on bio signals measured by electrodes. The positions of body parts could be tracked by processing these signals. Knowing neural signal patterns that force muscle actions and knowing the head “transfer function”, one could more precisely predict the future position and orientation of the head.

The output of computers can be directly connected to the human nerves: instead of building high resolution displays, images could be fed directly into the eye nerves, instead of providing force and tactile feedback, appropriate nerves in different parts of the body can be stimulated and so on.

3.2. Social aspects

Virtual reality, without doubt has a great energy to alter our life. People expect very much from this technology. Every new technology and every new experiment brings a fear and feeling of uncertainty with it. It can be used for good aim or it can be misused too.

VR has found already a large number of applications in different areas of science. It became a perfect tool for architects, designers, physicists, chemists, doctors, surgeons etc. All these fields, however, are closed for average people and something extremely wonderful and at the same time something inaccessible.

In the beginning of the current decade a great interest of media dragged it to the wide publicity. Moreover, the development of cheap and powerful hardware allowed the spread of many installations opened to the public. The first were arcade games computer games extended by an immersion feature using a HMD and a tracking system. The great success of them forced the market appearance of further entertainment systems: multi user car races, dungeon games, flight simulations and others.

There were already successful attempts of use of the VR systems in medicine e.g., curing of mental disorders, phobias, people with disabilities and in education. In the future, VR technology will have a rapidly growing influence on almost every area of our life. Then the use of virtual reality in everyday life will become as common as the use of TV-sets, telephones, videos, cars or airplanes today.

3.3 What are the fear factors of VR?

Virtual reality systems of the future can be divided into four groups according to two criteria: **social vs. non-social** and **creative vs. non-creative**. Non-social virtual realities allow a single user to interact with the environment. This can be an interaction either: with a pre programmed environment or with an environment that can be modified according to the user's needs and wishes.

Social virtual realities on the other hand allow multiple users to interact with each other and with the environment itself. Again, as with non-social systems, the environment can be pre programmed or it is created and altered by the user or a group of cooperating users.

Different types of VR systems can have different influences on people's mentality. Some of the most fanatic computer-game players can hardly be forced to come back to reality. With the improvement of the simulation and visual quality of virtual worlds the differences between reality and VR will be constantly disappearing and consequently people may become confused what is real and what is virtual. Military simulations are becoming so close to reality that soldiers do not know any more whether they are remotely steering a real

“death-machine” or just making training. VR may become the ultimate drug for the crowd. It is our responsibility to choose the right dose.

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